

ALISHER NAVAI'S NOBLE HUMAN VIRTUES IN “MAKARIM UL-AKHLAQ”

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the noble human virtues of Alisher Navai through Makorim ul-Akhloq, a work written by the historian Khondamir. The study mainly highlights Navai’s charitable deeds, his attitude toward people, and his belief in the equality of all individuals regardless of their social status or position. Furthermore, special attention is given to Navai’s constant efforts to improve his character and his ability to maintain self-control under all circumstances.

Introduction

The study of the great thinker Hazrat Alisher Navai, who had a very strong and effective influence on the formation of the spiritual world of the Turkic peoples, who occupied a high place in the consciousness and culture of our people, has been continuing for centuries. Since his living era, various works have been written about Navai. One of the most famous of them is considered Khandamir's "Makarim ul-akhloq", the writing of which began during Alisher Navai's lifetime and was completed after his death. This work is a book that contains Navai's scientific, literary, political and social activities, his importance in the life of the state, his great personality, his high human virtues, his incomparable services to the people of the country and science, and serves as a valuable source in studying various aspects of the poet. The work “Makarim ul-Akhloq” consists of an introduction, ten chapters, a conclusion, and a section on how Navoi died. This work can be viewed as a work written as a gratitude to the person who always supported and encouraged Khandamir. The extensive coverage of Navoi’s life and work in it increases the importance and value of the work in Navoi studies. “Makarim ul-Akhloq” covers Navai’s entire life and political activities, but the main focus is on highlighting his high features.

The work specifically focuses on Navoi's qualities such as nobility, humility, kindness, generosity, and always helping the people, and examples are given through stories.

Methods

This article is written analytically based on the famous historian Khondamir’s work “Makorim ul-akhloq” about Alisher Navai. At the same time, hermeneutic, analytical, discursive, and analysis-synthesis methods were widely used in the analysis process.

Results and Discussion

This emir, who was endowed with a karamat, during his career and position [in state affairs], built many houses, rabats, ponds, bridges, and baths in various parts of the Khurasan

country in order to provide material assistance to the poor and dervishes and create comfortable conditions for travelers and strangers [from other countries].¹

Here it can be seen that Navoi was a man of great generosity, and he never stopped extending a helping to ordinary people. At the same time, he built several madrasahs for the youth of the outside world or those who did not have the opportunity to study. His activities of this kind are described in the chapter entitled "On accumulating reserves for the Hereafter and turning away from this world and its things." In addition, through this information, one can also learn about Navai's religious and philosophical worldviews. According to the philosophical doctrine that Navai believed in, the universe is a mirror that emerged from the desire of the eternal Spirit to love itself and contemplate its own beauty. Also, in his attitude towards people and his movement towards perfection, the influence and strong manifestation of these same ideas can be seen. Navai belongs to the Naqshbandi order. This direction requires contentment and restraint, but does not prohibit enjoyment of the beauty of the world. Since the real world is an absolute reflection of the soul, it is possible to love the world and enjoy it. On this basis, love between people is also natural and necessary, that is, through figurative love, it leads to divine love. Navai also includes himself among such "figurative love" poets.²

Among human features, kindness and compassion are considered the highest qualities. These qualities in Navai should also be noted separately, because these qualities were at a high level in the Great Thinker. There were frequent internal and external wars in the Timurid empire. When the Emir's close friend Hussein Baykara won the battles, many people were taken prisoner. Navai tried to save the lives of the prisoners. At that time, it was not important for him who those people were, what was important that they were human. Navoi put human dignity, honor, and life above everything else.

"Once, the blessed mind of the Sultan Sahibkiran came to the idea of developing the Khorezm region, and he issued a decree that required the relocation of three thousand families from the population of Khurasan there. [According to this decree, these three thousand families were to settle in that region and devote their efforts to developing and farming there.]³

Hazrat Navai, a close friend and colleague of the Sultan, strongly opposed this idea and, using his right to appeal to the king nine times on one issue, called on the emir to think it over. And finally, this issue was accepted by the king. He decided that only one third of the three thousand families designated for the development of Khorezm would be sent.

From this we can see that Navoi always acted in the interests of the citizens. He took into account their wishes and tried to fulfill them.

Alisher Navai always tried to do good to people, to be humble, and to refrain from such habits as arrogance and pride as much as possible. According to the writings in "Makarim ul-Akhlaq", as the Amir's banner of power and influence rose, his humility and cheerfulness also increased. When he saw the grace and kindness shown to him by the great

¹ G'iyosiddin Xondamir. "Makarim ul-axloq". - Toshkent: "Yoshlar nashriyot uyi". 2018 - B. 12

² Najmiddin Komilov. "Tasavvuf". - Toshkent: "Movorounnahr"- "O'zbekiston". 2009. B.158.

³ G'iyosiddin Xondamir. "Makarim ul-axloq". - Toshkent: "Yoshlar nashriyot uyi". 2018 -B. 154.

ruler, Sahibkiran, increasing day by day, he would go somewhere in solitude, bow his head, and sprinkle some dust from the top of his blessed head.⁴

The reason for this was to prevent humility and arrogance, to consider himself the same as this soil, and to extinguish the fire of arrogance in his heart. Even when Sahibkiran Husayn Baykara offered him high positions, there were times when he refused these positions due to his humility. Despite his prestige and position in the kingdom, he did not refuse to listen to the complaints of the poor and ordinary people, and he considered their problems as his own and tried to find a solution. The emir was also famous among his contemporaries for his generosity.

During the reign of Sultan Abu Said, one Friday after praying in the mosque in the city of Herat, I set out with the intention of going to the square. When I was about to reach Masrakh Street, I saw a poor and destitute beggar sitting there, saying: "I am a married man, with several hungry and naked children. I have been sitting here begging since morning, but no one has given me a single coin yet."

At that time, I had only one coin with me, and apart from that, I did not have a single grain of the wealth that this world can acquire. Then I said to myself: "Put your trust in the Creator of all things, from the smallest particle to the largest, and give this coin to this beggar." I gave the coin to him and passed by. However, on my way back, I saw a beggar sitting in the same place, begging.⁵

Even though he had no money except for that coin, he gave it to him without hesitation after talking about his children. Even though he saw others repeatedly asking for money by saying the same things he had said to Navoi, he pretended not to see this situation so as not to embarrass him and put him in an awkward situation. This incident shows how generous he was.

In addition, Alisher Navai would allocate money from his own account when the people were in difficult situations and were struggling with taxes. He did his best to ensure that they did not remain in difficult situations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Navai's high human qualities have been highly appreciated in every era. Alisher Navai considered good character and virtues of a person as the highest value. Throughout his life, he further enriched his good qualities and beautiful deeds. Throughout his life, he tried to remain in the memory of people with his meritorious deeds. He worked tirelessly for the development of the country, for the people to live peacefully and prosperously without difficulties. Not only within the framework of his activities, but also in any situation, he put the interests of the people above his own interests. He tried to stay away from arrogance and conceit. Realizing that such qualities can harm the human psyche and derail it, he took the path of spiritual purification. His attitude towards people, regardless of their position and position, showing equal respect and good relations is another reason that led him to perfection. In his works, he also attaches special importance to the ideals of humanism.

⁴ G'iyosiddin Xondamir. "Makorim ul-axloq". - Toshkent: "Yoshlar nashriyot uyi". 2018. - B. 164.

⁵ G'iyosiddin Xondamir. "Makorim ul-axloq". - Toshkent: "Yoshlar nashriyot uyi". 2018. - B. 171.

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